

A STUDY OF ONLINE VIDEO CONSUMPTION BEHAVIOR THROUGH SOCIAL MEDIA AMONG GENERATION Z IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

The advancement of technology has also led to the increasing prominence of social media. The exposure to social media, particularly among Gen Z, has raised concerns about the potential for online video addiction on these platforms. This study aims to analyze the factors influencing social media use and its potential impact on online video addiction among Gen Z. The research employs a quantitative approach using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method. Data collection was conducted through a questionnaire completed by 400 respondents. The findings indicate that factors such as internet literacy and loneliness have a significant positive effect, whereas FOMO does not have a significant positive impact on social media use and the potential for online video addiction. Additionally, sensation seeking does not have a significant positive moderating effect on social media use and, therefore, does not influence the potential for online video addiction.

Keywords: *Internet Literacy, Loneliness, FOMO, Social Media Use, Online Video Addiction, Sensation Seeking*

1. INTRODUCTION

Every living being, including humans, has several basic needs, such as the need for nutritious food to meet daily intake, having a place to live, and wearing proper clothing. Among these essential needs, humans also have another necessity: entertainment. After a long day of work and tiring activities, enjoyable entertainment is essential to refresh the mind. Entertainment can be defined as a multidimensional construct that primarily describes a person's pleasurable experience when spending time with a particular medium. There are many types or forms of entertainment. In the past, entertainment was found in the form of television media, which included various talk shows, movies, soap operas, sports, and sitcoms. Over time, new entertainment media have emerged. The presence of social media and video games, supported by advanced technology, allows users to feel even more entertained [1]. Currently, entertainment is also very important and cannot be separated from our daily lives. After working hard at school or the workplace, entertainment can be an enjoyable way to take a break.

According to the Indonesia's Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS), in 2023, Indonesia had a

population of 278 million people. Of that number, 44 million were classified as young individuals (ages 15-24) according to the WHO definition, which is also considered a productive age group.

A survey conducted by the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII) on Indonesian internet behavior in 2023 collected data from 8,510 respondents. Among them, the age group between 19 and 34 years old constituted the second-largest majority, with a total of 3,243 respondents. APJII's findings show that 63.74% of respondents use the internet for 1-5 hours per day, while other data indicate that a total of 29.58% of respondents use the internet for more than 6 hours per day. APJII also found that social media, online gaming, and online streaming are the most accessed entertainment content where watching online videos through social media ranked the highest, reaching 55%. APJII also stated that the most used social media platforms for watching videos and accessing other content are YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok.

Anything done in excess is certainly not good, and this also applies to the use of social media for accessing various online content. Data compiled by APJII indicates that 46.16% of people spend 1-2 hours per day on social media, 25.14% use it for 2-

3 hours, 8.46% for 3-4 hours, and 7.84% for more than 4 hours a day. This data shows that many Indonesians spend a significant amount of time on social media daily. Considering that a day consists of 24 hours, some individuals spend 1/6 of their day solely on accessing and using social media. This can be identified as a phenomenon of internet and social media addiction.

In 2023, Deloitte conducted a survey to assess the mental health conditions of Generation Z. The findings from the survey revealed that 46% of Gen Z experience mental health issues, including high stress levels and anxiety. Various factors contribute to this phenomenon, such as increased life pressures, rising living costs, and other stressors. The rise of social media has significantly impacted entertainment consumption, particularly among Generation Z. Prior studies have explored the impact of social media usage on mental health and addiction patterns as 22.7% of Gen Z who are addicted to social media show poorer mental health conditions [2]. However, these studies primarily focused on social media use broadly without specifically addressing online video consumption. Therefore, this study aims to understand the factors influencing social media addiction, particularly video-watching behavior among Generation Z in Indonesia. The phenomenon of internet and social media addiction has become increasingly common in recent times. This issue arises as certain groups of people spend a significant portion of their day engaging in these activities, which also impact their mental health. This study explores how the characteristics and habits by examining internet literacy, loneliness, FOMO, and sensation seeking as key influencing factors on social media use and online video addiction of Generation Z in Indonesia. Additionally, it examines the factors that contribute to social media addiction, particularly in relation to video-watching behavior among Generation Z in Indonesia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Entertainment

Entertainment plays an equally important role as other basic needs, as it provides a way to relieve fatigue and stress after engaging in various exhausting activities. It can be described as an activity that generates external stimuli, evoking both positive and negative emotions while engaging the audience [3]. Thus, it can be said that with this entertainment, the audience can feel entertained by the content being shared.

Entertainment has the absolute and primary purpose of providing pleasure and enjoyment to its audience. However, its function or purpose is not limited to merely delivering enjoyment; entertainment has a broader scope of functions. It also serves an educational role, meaning that educational content is expected to have an informative impact, covering aspects such as cultural knowledge, life lessons, historical events, and more.

Another function of entertainment is as a bridge or connector between individuals or groups. In society, there are various groups with different backgrounds, but these differences can be united through shared entertainment or hobbies. Entertainment can also be positioned as a cultural reflection, as it mirrors and shapes the norms and values of a society. This occurs because entertainment can indirectly influence social trends and public behavior [4].

Entertainment has existed since ancient times, and as time progresses, it continues to evolve and develop. The emergence of new forms of entertainment, such as video games and social media, has grown increasingly popular in society [5]. In the past, entertainment was very limited, starting with theatrical performances before evolving into radio, television, and eventually the internet. Entertainment is a unique form of public communication due to its aesthetic characteristics and its ability to evoke emotional impressions [6].

Recently, various social media platforms have emerged. The presence of these platforms has undoubtedly impacted different layers of society. This happens because entertainment content is carefully packaged and supported by the latest technology, making it more accessible to the public. Various types of content, including photos, videos, and more, are now easily accessible with just an internet connection and a connected device.

2.2 Addiction

Anything consumed or used excessively is never good and can lead to negative impacts. This also applies to entertainment when consumed excessively, it can be harmful. If someone becomes overly attached to something, there is a high possibility that they are experiencing a condition known as addiction. Addiction itself can be defined as a complex and chronic disorder that affects parts of the brain related to reward, motivation, and memory. This condition can lead to an inability to control behavior and cause changes in behavioral patterns. Addiction can be characterized by a compulsive urge to seek and use a substance

without the ability to control it. If access to the substance is restricted or prevented, the person may experience negative emotional responses. This occurs because the substance affects the body and alters brain function, leading to dependency and withdrawal symptoms.

Addiction is not limited to the use of illegal drugs; it can occur in various forms, one of which is social media addiction. Social media addiction is characterized by excessive use and emotional involvement with social media. With the abundance of entertainment content available on these platforms, addiction can easily develop. Individuals experiencing social media addiction are often associated with poorer sleep quality, lower self-esteem, higher stress levels, and increased feelings of anxiety and depression [7]. The concerning aspect of social media addiction is that it is frequently observed among younger age groups, which can significantly impact their growth and mental health.

Like other types of addiction, social media addiction can arise due to various factors. A lack of self-discipline plays a significant role in the development of this addiction. The ease of access to entertainment content on social media platforms further exacerbates the issue. When an individual becomes addicted to social media, it inevitably affects their quality of life, as multiple aspects can be impacted. These include physical health problems, difficulties in social interactions, and challenges in education and employment [8].

2.3 Internet Literacy

In this study, internet literacy is one of the independent variables. This variable includes knowledge and skills in using the internet effectively, the ability to access, analyze, and utilize online information, as well as an understanding of both the benefits and risks associated with the internet. Additionally, self-regulation in managing internet usage is also a key component of this variable [9].

2.4 Loneliness

The variable loneliness in this study serves as an independent variable. It encompasses the subjective and unpleasant feeling resulting from a lack of social connections. Loneliness can influence a person's behavior, such as excessive social media use and increased levels of anxiety [10].

2.5 FOMO

FOMO (Feeling of Missing Out) is one of the independent variables in this study. It refers to a

state of anxiety caused by the fear of missing out on beneficial experiences, which drives individuals to engage more actively in social media. The presence of FOMO can influence teenagers' sleep behavior, as it encourages social media use late at night [11].

2.6 Social Media Use

Social media use serves as a mediating variable in this study. It is adapted from the broader concept of internet use. This variable encompasses aspects such as the duration of social media usage and the purpose or orientation behind its use.

2.7 Sensation Seeking

Sensation seeking is a moderating variable in this study, meaning it can strengthen or weaken the relationships between other variables. This variable aims to measure the strong desire to engage in certain activities, often combined with a tendency to take risks to achieve specific experiences. In the context of this study, it assesses whether the relationship between social media use and online video addiction can be moderated [12].

2.8 Online Video Addiction

Online video addiction serves as the dependent variable in this study. It is adapted from the broader concept of internet addiction [9]. This variable refers to an individual's tendency to lose control over their online behavior, particularly in watching online videos. Short-form videos are among the most addictive types, as their immersive nature encourages users to keep watching continuously [13]. Short-form video content on social media contributes to addiction levels in individuals, partly due to personalization that tailors content based on their preferences [14].

3. METHODOLOGY

The research problem was selected based on the growing concern surrounding excessive online video consumption among Gen Z in Indonesia, as evidenced by statistical reports from APJII (2023) and Deloitte (2023). These findings show that high internet and social media usage among young individuals, with potential negative effects on mental health. Literature used in this research was screened based on relevance to online video addiction, social media behavior, and mental health implications by selecting journals and articles in the last 10 years.

This is a quantitative research that utilized a survey or questionnaire to gather the required data. The subject of this research is Gen Z from 12-27 years old in Indonesia. Survey or questionnaire

is shared through google form across multiple social media platforms, for instance Instagram, line, and whatsapp. The survey contains a total of 39 questions which divided for each variable having likert scale from 1-4. Where 1 is strongly disagree and 4 is strongly agree.

the technique used in this survey is simple random sampling. The population in this survey is Gen Z in Indonesia, as in 2023, the number of Gen Z in Indonesia is nearly 75 million people or nearly 27% of Indonesia's total resident. In order to determine the right sample for this research, Slovin formula is used, which resulted in 400 minimal required sample.

Structured Equation Model – Partial Least Square or SEM-PLS is used as data analysis method, data analysis will be run using software called SMART-PLS version 4.0. Below is the figure of the research model.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Based on the conceptual framework above, here are the hypotheses in this research:

H1: Internet literacy in social media usage has a positive influence on social media use.

H2: Loneliness in social media usage has a positive influence on social media use.

H3: FOMO in social media usage has a positive influence on social media use.

H4: Social media use has a positive influence on online video addiction.

H5: Sensation seeking moderates the influence of social media use on online video addiction.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Demography of Respondents

Data collection was conducted from November 21, 2024, to November 30, 2024. During this period, approximately 400 respondents were successfully gathered. The following is a breakdown of the respondents' profiles or demographics:

Table 1. Demography of Respondents

Description		Respondents (Person)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	186	46.5%
	Female	214	53.5%
Age	<12 years	0	0
	12-27 years	400	100%
	28-43 years	0	0
	44-59 years	0	0
	60-78 years	0	0
	>79 years	0	0
Education Background	Did Not Complete Elementary School	0	0
	Elementary School	0	0
	Junior High School	16	4%
	Senior High School	200	50%
	Bachelor or Diploma	176	44%
	Master Degree	8	2%
	Doctorate Degree	0	0
Occupation	Student or college student	216	54%
	Housewife	10	2.5%
	Civil servant	6	1.5%
	Private sector employee	148	37%
	Entrepreneur	8	2%
	Not working/ Retired	0	0
	Professional	12	3%
Social Media Owned	Youtube	181	-
	Facebook	195	-
	Instagram	338	-
	TikTok	262	-
	Whatsapp	82	-
	Twitter	39	-
Frequency of Social Media Use	Daily	400	100%
	More than once a week	0	0
	Several times a month	0	0
	Less than once a month	0	0
Daily Duration of Social Media Use	<30 minutes	0	0
	30-60 minutes	11	2.8%
	1-2 hours	31	7.8%
	2-3 hours	0	0
	>3 hours	356	89%
Purpose of Social Media Use	Spending free time	124	-
	Listen to music	77	-
	Reading news	50	-
	Internet shopping	85	-
	Content creation	74	-
	Chatting	74	-
	Academic purpose	48	-
	Work purpose	63	-

4.2 Measurement Model: Validity & Reliability

This study will use several measurement methodology to evaluate the validity and reliability of all indicators, ensuring the accuracy of the proposed hypotheses. To assess convergent validity, it can be measured using loading factor and AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value. Loading factor value should be >0.7 and AVE value should be >0.5.

Table 2. Loading Factor

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	AVE
Internet Literacy	IL1	0.844	0.719
	IL2	0.852	
	IL3	0.856	
	IL4	0.846	
	IL5	0.843	
	IL6	0.848	
Loneliness	L1	0.838	0.697
	L2	0.828	
	L3	0.831	
	L4	0.840	
	L5	0.834	
	L6	0.837	
FOMO	F1	0.735	0.671
	F2	0.707	
	F3	0.950	
	F4	0.861	
Social Media Use	SMU1	0.824	0.687
	SMU2	0.823	
	SMU3	0.822	
	SMU4	0.826	
	SMU5	0.838	
	SMU6	0.833	
	SMU7	0.831	
	SMU8	0.836	
	SMU9	0.826	
Online Video Addiction	OVA1	0.813	0.660
	OVA2	0.829	
	OVA3	0.814	
	OVA4	0.790	
	OVA5	0.823	
	OVA6	0.806	
	OVA7	0.810	
	OVA8	0.817	
	OVA9	0.812	
Sensation Seeking	SS1	0.986	0.966
	SS2	0.980	
	SS4	0.981	

To assess discriminant validity, it can be measured by using cross loading and fornell lecker. Based on Tables 3 and 4, the data used in this study

demonstrates good discriminant validity. This is evident from the cross-loading results, where the indicator values of a variable are higher than those of other variables. Additionally, the Fornell-Larcker criterion results show that each variable's value is higher than the values of other variables in the same column.

Table 3. Cross Loading

	FOMO	IL	L	OVA	SMU	SS
F1	0,735	0,036	0,015	0,556	0,010	0,443
F2	0,707	0,023	-0,023	0,571	0,001	0,458
F3	0,950	0,083	-0,025	0,524	0,045	0,460
F4	0,861	0,051	0,000	0,555	0,024	0,451
IL1	0,065	0,844	-0,613	0,016	0,631	-0,131
IL2	0,085	0,852	-0,631	0,021	0,621	-0,208
IL3	0,076	0,856	-0,669	0,009	0,655	-0,232
IL4	0,067	0,846	-0,629	0,039	0,617	-0,165
IL5	0,043	0,843	-0,655	0,002	0,619	-0,239
IL6	0,046	0,848	-0,638	-0,041	0,651	-0,198
L1	-0,003	-0,631	0,838	0,071	-0,653	0,229
L2	-0,004	-0,623	0,828	-0,012	-0,642	0,193
L3	-0,001	-0,639	0,831	-0,012	-0,667	0,279
L4	0,007	-0,635	0,840	0,005	-0,664	0,215
L5	-0,051	-0,637	0,834	0,008	-0,659	0,237
L6	-0,019	-0,610	0,837	0,007	-0,638	0,216
OVA1	0,491	0,050	-0,024	0,813	0,029	0,398
OVA2	0,530	0,031	-0,034	0,829	0,041	0,457
OVA3	0,470	-0,051	0,052	0,814	-0,007	0,437
OVA4	0,459	-0,042	0,051	0,790	-0,033	0,358
OVA5	0,477	0,032	0,018	0,823	0,021	0,467
OVA6	0,476	-0,034	0,014	0,806	-0,001	0,431
OVA7	0,505	-0,018	0,053	0,810	-0,021	0,457
OVA8	0,497	0,040	-0,002	0,817	0,024	0,410
OVA9	0,483	0,045	-0,024	0,812	0,036	0,404
SMU1	0,101	0,617	-0,633	0,058	0,824	-0,200
SMU2	0,005	0,623	-0,643	-0,002	0,823	-0,247
SMU3	0,034	0,586	-0,647	0,014	0,822	-0,229
SMU4	0,011	0,602	-0,645	0,000	0,826	-0,283
SMU5	0,039	0,636	-0,666	0,020	0,838	-0,219
SMU6	0,020	0,618	-0,653	0,005	0,833	-0,225
SMU7	0,078	0,608	-0,647	0,042	0,831	-0,230
SMU8	-0,008	0,659	-0,670	-0,014	0,836	-0,254
SMU9	0,007	0,615	-0,641	-0,024	0,826	-0,254
SS1	0,490	-0,237	0,284	0,512	-0,293	0,986
SS2	0,506	-0,218	0,263	0,518	-0,272	0,980
SS4	0,503	-0,225	0,260	0,517	-0,282	0,981

Table 4. Fornell Lecker

	FOMO	IL	L	OVA	SMU	SS
FOMO	0,819					
IL	0,075	0,848				
L	-0,014	-0,754	0,835			
OVA	0,601	0,008	0,014	0,813		
SMU	0,038	0,746	-0,784	0,013	0,829	
SS	0,509	-0,231	0,274	0,525	-0,287	0,983

A reliability test also needs to be carried out by using Cronbach Alpha value and composite reliability value. Based on the Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability calculations in Table 5, the data in this study demonstrates good reliability. This is supported by the fact that the Cronbach's alpha value is greater than 0.5 and the composite reliability value exceeds 0.6.

Table 5. Construct Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Composite Reliability
Internet Literacy (IL)	0,922	0.939
Loneliness (L)	0.913	0.932
FOMO	0.871	0.889
Social Media Use (SMU)	0.943	0.952
Online Video Addiction (OVA)	0.936	0.946
Sensation Seeking (SS)	0.982	0.988

4.3 R-square Testing

The R-square measurement aims to determine the extent to which independent variables in the research model influence the dependent variable. Based on the R-square value in table 6, 30% of the variability in Online Video Addiction (OVA) can be explained by the independent variables in the model, while the remaining 70% is influenced by factors outside the research model. Similarly, 66% of the variability in Social Media Use (SMU) can be explained by the independent variables in this study, with the remaining 34% influenced by other factors outside the model.

Table 6. R-Square

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Online Video Addiction	0.306	0.301
Social Media Use	0.670	0.668

4.4. Hypothesis Testing

In hypothesis testing in table 7 using coefficient calculations, the most important aspects to consider are the T-Statistic and P-value. A T-Statistic greater than 1.96 indicates that the research hypothesis or the relationship between variables is accepted. Additionally, the hypothesis is also supported if the P-value is less than 0.05, confirming the significance of the relationship between variables.

Table 7. Path Coefficient

Hypothesis	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
H1 IL → SMU	4.379	0.000
H2 L → SMU	6.299	0.000
H3 FOMO → SMU	0.060	0.952

H4	SMU → OVA	2.815	0.005
H5	SS X SMU → OVA	0.525	0.600

4.5. Discussion

Based on the result mentioned in the previous section, there are 3 hypotheses out of 5 that are positively significant towards online video addiction. It can be seen through the value of its T-statistic and P-value.

First H1, The first hypothesis test examines the effect of internet literacy on social media use. The H1 hypothesis test results show a T-Statistic value greater than 1.96, specifically 4.379, and a P-value less than 0.05, specifically 0.000. This indicates that internet literacy has a significant positive influence on social media use.

Second H2, The second hypothesis test examines the effect of loneliness on social media use. The H2 hypothesis test results show a T-Statistic value greater than 1.96, specifically 6.299, and a P-value less than 0.05, specifically 0.000. This indicates that loneliness has a significant positive influence on social media use.

Third H3, The third hypothesis test examines the effect of FOMO on social media use. The H3 hypothesis test results show a T-Statistic value less than 1.96, specifically 0.060, and a P-value greater than 0.05, specifically 0.952. This indicates that FOMO does not have a significant positive influence on social media use. Certain characteristics of FOMO, such as fear and anxiety when others have more enjoyable experiences on social media, do not significantly impact social media usage. Respondents in the survey also tend to be less concerned about the activities of others or their friends on social media.

Fourth H4, The fourth hypothesis test examines the effect of social media use on online video addiction. The H4 hypothesis test results show a T-Statistic value greater than 1.96, specifically 2.815, and a P-value less than 0.05, specifically 0.005. This indicates that social media use has a significant positive influence on online video addiction.

Fifth H5, The fifth hypothesis test examines the moderating effect of sensation seeking on the relationship between social media

use and online video addiction. The H5 hypothesis test results show a T-Statistic value less than 1.96, specifically 0.525, and a P-value greater than 0.05, specifically 0.600. This indicates that sensation seeking does not have a significant positive moderating effect on the relationship between social media use and online video addiction. These findings suggest that the majority of respondents' social media usage does not indicate characteristics of sensation seeking. Traits such as impulsivity and the consumption of challenging or controversial content were also not evident in this study.

4.6 Implications

The results found in this research indicate that there are several findings that may disrupt daily activities and also may cause possible health issues. In order to prevent that, there are several recommendations that can be considered.

To address loneliness, individuals can engage in various positive activities and seek communities that align with their personalities, which may help reduce feelings of isolation.

To mitigate excessive social media use, which increases the likelihood of online video addiction, social media applications or platforms can implement several policies. These include providing notifications about an individual's daily screen time, implementing more accurate content categorization to minimize irrelevant content appearing on users' social media feeds, and developing optional features that allow users to limit their access or usage based on the time spent on the platform.

Additionally, promoting awareness of responsible social media usage should be carried out more broadly across Indonesia to reduce the risk of addiction resulting from excessive social media consumption.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the research conducted, several conclusions can be drawn. First, the study identified various characteristics and habits of Gen Z that contribute to social media addiction, particularly in the activity of watching short online videos. The majority of respondents have more than one social media platform and use them daily for over three hours. This usage is driven by several reasons, but the main one is to pass the time. The study shows that respondents have good internet literacy, as they are able to use the internet effectively and find the information they need by utilizing appropriate

software and hardware. On the other hand, although a small percentage, some respondents indicated feelings of loneliness, which increased the potential for social media use. Additionally, some respondents showed signs of FOMO (Fear of Missing Out), particularly regarding social media.

Social media usage has become an integral part of the respondents' lives, and they indicated that they use it for various purposes. Respondents also use social media to find and discover necessary information and to communicate with others. The extensive use of social media led respondents to develop a dependence, especially in entertainment activities such as watching short videos on social media. This has resulted in addiction to consuming short videos. Various indicators suggest that watching online videos is done to achieve satisfaction. However, this can sometimes have negative effects, as seen in the impact on daily activities like work or study, and the potential for health issues.

This study critically examines the factors influencing online video addiction among Generation Z in Indonesia, with a specific focus on internet literacy, loneliness, FOMO, social media use, and sensation seeking. The findings confirm that internet literacy and loneliness significantly contribute to increased social media use, which in turn leads to online video addiction. However, FOMO was found to have no significant impact, contradicting earlier studies that suggested otherwise. Similarly, sensation seeking did not moderate the relationship between social media use and online video addiction, indicating that habitual video consumption may not necessarily be driven by thrill or sensation seeking tendencies.

This research findings shows that online video addiction can be driven by several reasons. It can be driven internally through person's habit and characteristics and also externally through nearby environment. Many ways can be used to prevent or mitigate online video addiction, as research results offer actionable insights for policymakers, mental health professionals, and social media platforms.

This research makes a significant contribution by providing an in-depth analysis of online video addiction especially short video form from an Indonesian's Generation Z context, an area that remains underexplored in existing literature. This knowledge is crucial for developing targeted interventions to promote healthier digital habits among Indonesian's Generation Z.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. Vorderer, “It’s all entertainment-sure. But what exactly is entertainment? Communication research, media psychology, and the explanation of entertainment experiences,” 2001. [Online]. Available: www.elsevier.com/locate/poetic
- [2] C. Eichenberg, R. Schneider, and H. Rimpl, “Social media addiction: associations with attachment style, mental distress, and personality,” *BMC Psychiatry*, vol. 24, no. 1, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1186/s12888-024-05709-z.
- [3] L. Benny, “Entertainment Studies – A Perspective,” 2015, [Online]. Available: www.iasir.net,
- [4] M. B. Oliver and A. A. Raney, “An introduction to the special issue: Expanding the boundaries of entertainment research,” *Journal of Communication*, vol. 64, no. 3, pp. 361–368, 2014, doi: 10.1111/jcom.12092.
- [5] R. Nakatsu, “Logos, Pathos, and Entertainment,” 2010.
- [6] M. IONIȚĂ and V. PĂSTAE, “ENTERTAINMENT AS A STANCE OF PUBLIC COMMUNICATION,” *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE “STRATEGIESXXI,”* vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 86–91, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.53477/2971-8813-22-09.
- [7] Y. Tri Prasetyo, P. Tejero, A. Rose Paras, and M. S. Allyson Pear Garcia, “The Impact of Social Media to Addictive Behavior and Mental Health Issues: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach,” in *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, Association for Computing Machinery, Apr. 2021, pp. 173–179. doi: 10.1145/3460824.3460851.
- [8] F. Nazir, N. Omar, M. A. Aripin, M. Hizwan, and M. Hisham, “A Case Study of Social Media Addiction Among Malaysians,” 2020. [Online]. Available: www.solidstatetechnology.us
- [9] Q. Jiang, Z. Chen, Z. Zhang, and C. Zuo, “Investigating links between Internet literacy, Internet use, and Internet addiction among Chinese youth and adolescents in the digital age,” *Front Psychiatry*, vol. 14, 2023, doi: 10.3389/fpsy.2023.1233303.
- [10] V. Boursier, F. Gioia, A. Musetti, and A. Schimmenti, “Facing Loneliness and Anxiety During the COVID-19 Isolation: The Role of Excessive Social Media Use in a Sample of Italian Adults,” *Front Psychiatry*, vol. 11, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.3389/fpsy.2020.586222.
- [11] H. Scott and H. C. Woods, “Fear of missing out and sleep: Cognitive behavioural factors in adolescents’ nighttime social media use,” *J Adolesc*, vol. 68, pp. 61–65, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2018.07.009.
- [12] B. Gao, Y. Cai, C. Zhao, Y. Qian, R. Zheng, and C. Liu, “Longitudinal associations between loneliness and online game addiction among undergraduates: A moderated mediation model,” *Acta Psychol (Amst)*, vol. 243, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.actpsy.2024.104134.
- [13] L. Lu, M. Liu, B. Ge, Z. Bai, and Z. Liu, “Adolescent Addiction to Short Video Applications in the Mobile Internet Era,” *Front Psychol*, vol. 13, May 2022, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.893599.
- [14] X. Zhang, Y. Wu, and S. Liu, “Exploring short-form video application addiction: Socio-technical and attachment perspectives,” *Telematics and Informatics*, vol. 42, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.tele.2019.101243.